

MULTISCALE MODELING OF NON LINEAR BEHAVIOUR IN VARIOUS COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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SUMMARY

Composite materials are more and more used in aeronautical applications. The study of the strength of these structures is a multiscale problem. The aim of this work is to model several structures (using the finite element method) reinforced by composite materials taking into account all pertinent levels. Various techniques can be used to model the macroscopic composite behaviour. They are respectively based on

* The use of a classical macroscopic model which is developed and identified using experimental results.

* The use of a ``macroscopic multiscale`` model which is derived from scales transitions and `` keeps in memory `` the microscopic scale. The composite is thus described at the structural scale as an homogenous medium. This of modeling is called ``sequential approach``.

* The resolution of the constitutive laws at the local scale using different change of scale methods. These kind of methods are called ``integrated approaches``.

Different approaches are compared, in structural calculations, in terms of computational cost, macroscopic results and local quantities. The first example is devoted to the modelling of an integrally bladed ring reinforced by a SiC/Ti composite. The second example is devoted to the modelling of a structure reinforced by a polymer matrix composite.

INTRODUCTION

Composite materials are more and more used in aerospace. However, the use of these materials is still limited due to their complex deformation and failure mechanisms leading to a large safety margin in the structure design. It is thus a great challenge to develop models of the mechanical behaviour of these materials. Classically, purely macroscopic models are used for practical applications. In the past few years, models are developed, based on micromechanical considerations. This approach seems to be particularly well adapted to composite materials, the latter being characterised by the level of the structure, the level of the laminate, the level of the unidirectional ply and finally the local level (fibre/matrix scale).

The aim of this work is to model several structures reinforced by composite materials, taking into account all pertinent levels. Many steps are necessary to reach this goal : (i) define a Representative Volume Element, (ii) define the pertinent scale (defined by the damage and deformation mechanisms), (iii) identify the behaviour of each constituents, (iv) develop the macroscopic behaviour using scale transitions.

This kind of complete multiscale approach is presented in this paper and applied to two different industrial composites materials. The first is a SiC/Ti composite that is a good candidate for several aeronautical applications, such as unidirectional reinforcement of integrally bladed compressor rings [1]. The second is a polymer matrix composite which is envisaged to be used for structural parts of supersonic civil planes. Classically these composites are used as unidirectional ply laminates.

This paper is divided into four sections. Section 2 of this paper presents the experimental and numerical procedure. For the scale transitions, the Transformation Field Analysis is used (section 3).

Section 4 deals with the modelling of composite behaviour using these methods and compares the results with experiments. Finally, section 5 is devoted to applications to structural modelling.

EXPERIMENTAL AND NUMERICAL PROCEDURE

Multiscale approaches are based on the knowledge of the deformation and damage mechanisms at different scales. This part is therefore devoted to the presentation of these mechanisms for the materials under investigation; the pertinent scales and the constitutive law of each constituents are thus defined.

Figure 1 : Pertinent scales for the two materials under investigation.

1. Titanium matrix reinforced by SiC fibres

The material under investigation is a SM1140+/Ti-6242 composite. The matrix is a near α titanium alloy Ti-6242 (Ti-6Al-2Sn-4Zr-2Mo, wt%). The reinforcement is a SM1140+ fibre produced by Chemical Vapour Deposition (CVD) by QinetiQ (UK). The SiC sheath (98 μm in diameter) is deposited by CVD on a tungsten core and further coated with a 4.5 μm two-layer pure carbon. The composite is manufactured by Snecma using a complex thermo-mechanical fabrication process (950°C, 80MPa) under vacuum.

The macroscopic composite behaviour can be described by a damageable elasto-viscoplastic model. The viscoplastic behaviour is due to the behaviour of the matrix. The damage mechanisms are located in the fibre (rupture of fibre in the longitudinal direction) or at the fibre/matrix interface

(interface debonding in the transverse direction). This composite being used as unidirectional reinforcement, a two-scale approach can be considered for this composite : micro/meso (figure 1).

In this paper, the SiC fiber is described by a transversely isotropic elastic law. The Ti-alloy matrix is characterized by an isotropic elasto-viscoplastic law, and the interfacial behavior is described by a debonding law. An important effort has been devoted to the identification of the mechanical behaviour of each constituent.

2. Polymer matrix composites

The material under investigation is the IMS/977-2 composite which is a carbon-fibre/polymer resin composites. It was manufactured industrially with a post-cure cycle of two hours at 210°C. Several stack sequences have been studied. This material is envisaged to be used for some structural parts of a supersonic civil transport plane.

Studies have shown that the composite behaviour depends on the stack sequence. However, it is well known that the composite behaviour can be described by a damageable non-linear viscoelastic model. The non-linearities (damage or viscosity) are located in the matrix. This composite being used as laminate with complex stack sequence, a three-scale approach is used : micro/meso and meso/macro (figure 1).

In this paper, the carbon-fibre behaviour is considered to be elastic isotropic, and the polymer matrix has a non-linear viscoelastic behaviour. The model chosen to describe the matrix behaviour has been established in a thermodynamical context. For the sake of simplicity, in this paper, the applied loads have been chosen in order to remain in the undamaged part of the composite behaviour.

METHODS FOR CHANGE OF SCALE

The aim of multiscale approaches is to describe the mechanical behaviour of a structure from the local constitutive equations of each constituents. This can be achieved in several ways, for example by modelling all the heterogeneities in the structure [2], or modelling the heterogeneities using particular finite elements [3]. In this paper, however, a different approach is chosen.

Two scales are considered simultaneously. A computation of the entire structure is carried out, but at each Gauss point of this macroscopic scale, the constitutive equations are replaced by a calculation at the microscopic scale.

1. Basics of the TFA method

The majority of change of scales methods are based on a Representative Volume Element (RVE) which describe the whole material microstructure. This volume can be divided in a number of sub-volumes (V_r), inside which the mechanical fields are supposed uniform.

In the case of pure elasticity, the microscopic stress and strain fields ($\boldsymbol{\sigma}_r$ and $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_r$) are connected to the macroscopic ones ($\boldsymbol{\Sigma}$ and \boldsymbol{E}) by the classical relations:

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}_r = \mathbf{B}_r : \boldsymbol{\Sigma} \quad (1)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_r = \mathbf{A}_r : \boldsymbol{E} \quad (2)$$

where the fourth rank tensors \mathbf{A}_r and \mathbf{B}_r are the elastic strain and stress concentration tensors respectively of the sub-volume V_r .

Equations (1) and (2) are no longer valid if one or several sub-volumes develop non-linearities. Dvorak proposed to correct these relations in order to take into account the influence of a uniform

plastic strain in the sub-volume s , on the sub-volume r . The complete demonstration is given by Dvorak [4,5] The local stress and strain fields are connected to the macroscopic ones by relations using influence tensors noted \mathbf{F}_{rs} and \mathbf{D}_{rs} ; the subscript rs denotes the influence of the sub-volume s on the sub-volume r . These tensors depend on the elastic behavior of each sub-volume and on the shape of the RVE, and have to be determined only once, independently of the inelastic process.

In case of varying local elastic behaviour (induced by change of temperature or damage) these tensors must be recalculated at each increment of the problem. Pottier [6] and Chaboche *et al.* [7] have modified the TFA model to correct this problem. The local stress field is connected to the macroscopic one by the relation :

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}_r = \mathbf{B}_r : \boldsymbol{\Sigma} - \sum_{s=1}^n \mathbf{F}_{rs} : (\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_s^g) \quad (3)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_r = \mathbf{A}_r : \mathbf{E} + \sum_{s=1}^n \mathbf{D}_{rs} : (\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_s^g) \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{F}_{rs} and \mathbf{D}_{rs} are respectively the stress and strain influence tensors. $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_s^g$ denotes the generalized eigenstrain which takes into account all the non linearities. The eigenstrain is obtained as follows :

$$\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_s^g = (\mathbf{I} - \tilde{\mathbf{L}}_s^{-1} : \mathbf{L}_s^0) : (\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_s - \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_s^{in} - \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_s^{th}) \quad (5)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_s^{in}$ and $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_s^{th}$ denote respectively the inelastic and the thermal strains of the sub-volumes s . $\tilde{\mathbf{L}}_s$ and \mathbf{L}_s^0 are respectively the actual and the initial stiffness tensor of the sub-volume s .

Finally, the macroscopic behavior can be obtained by averaging the local stresses on the RVE :

$$\boldsymbol{\Sigma} = \left\langle \boldsymbol{\sigma}(x) \right\rangle_V = \sum_r c_r \boldsymbol{\sigma}_r \quad (6)$$

$$\mathbf{E} = \left\langle \boldsymbol{\epsilon}(x) \right\rangle_V = \sum_r c_r \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_r \quad (7)$$

where c_r is the volume fraction of the sub-volume V_r ($c_r = V_r/V$).

Note that the main difficulty of this method is the calculation of the localisation and influence tensors. They are determined just once, by solving a set of linear problems (6 for the concentration tensors and $6*N$ for the influence tensors) by a finite element method.

2. Analytical determination of relations

In some cases, it is possible to determine the localisation and the influence tensors using analytical relations. For example, in the micro/meso change of scales, if the RVE is divided in two sub-volumes (one for the fibre and one for the matrix), one can obtain :

$$\mathbf{D}_{sr} = (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{A}_s) : (\mathbf{L}_s - \mathbf{L}^{hom})^{-1} : (\delta_{sr} \mathbf{I} - c_r \mathbf{A}_r^t) : \mathbf{L}_r \quad (8)$$

$$\mathbf{F}_{sr} = (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{B}_s) : (\mathbf{S}_s - \mathbf{S}^{hom})^{-1} : (\delta_{sr} \mathbf{I} - c_r \mathbf{B}_r^t) : \mathbf{S}_r \quad (9)$$

where δ_{sr} is the Kronecker symbol (1 if $s=r$, 0 in the other cases). \mathbf{L}^{hom} is the overall stiffness tensor, and $\mathbf{S} = \mathbf{L}^{-1}$. No summation is indicated by the repeated subscripts. Localisation tensors \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} can be obtained using the self-consistent of Mori-Tanaka method [6].

3. Sequential and integrated method

Two ways are possible to use the TFA method :

- The “integrated approach” consists in solving the constitutive laws at the local scale. This method is divided into three steps : 1. localization, 2. constitutive equations at the local scale and 3. homogenization.
- The “sequential approach” consists in using a ”macroscopic multiscale” model which is derived from multiscale passages given by the TFA method. The behaviour of the unidirectional composite is thus described as homogenous medium. Example of such models can be found in [8] for SiC/Ti composite and in [9] for Polymer-matrix composites.

These two methods have been implemented in the general purpose Finite Element code ZéBuLoN[10].

The integrated approach consists of a toolbox called “MULTIMAT”. The main idea is to let the user define his own multiscale materials by (1) choosing the constitutive behaviour of each sub-volume and (2) choosing a method to evaluate the localisation and the influence tensors for the TFA method (Mori-Tanaka, self-consistent, numeric ...).

The sequential approach consists in developing a macroscopic constitutive model obtained from a micromechanical analysis using the TFA method. Theoretically, this can be done with any number of sub-volumes, but in practice it is just done for a low number of sub-volumes. Usually this leads to a too stiff behaviour. A correction method must then be applied (see [11] for example). The sequential method necessitates some manipulation of equations, but it leads to a model “classical in its form” which can be “easily” implemented in any Finite Element code.

MODELLING OF COMPOSITE BEHAVIOUR

In this part a sequential modelling is applied to two different classes of composites : SiC/Ti and polymer matrix composites. The number of sub-volumes is fixed to two in order to obtain a simple model which can be easily implemented and used in a finite element code.

1. SiC/Ti composite :

As explained in the introduction, SiC/Ti composite are characterised by both damage and plastic deformation mechanisms.

The matrix behaviour is described by an elasto-viscoplastic model identified on a monolithic matrix by tensile [12], cyclic [13] and creep [8] tests, for temperatures ranging from 20° to 900°C. Damage is introduced in the fibre in order to describe the interfacial debonding. The damage model is based on Continuum Damage Mechanics (CDM) concepts, the equations of which can be found in [8]. This very simple model, introduced in the fibre at the microscopic scale, leads to complex effects at the macroscopic scale. The damage model, in the fibre plane, has been identified using virtual experiments where all constituents are considered as elastic and the interface is described by a cohesive zone model identified from Push-Out tests [8]. The evolution of the axial damage variable (rupture of fibre) has been identified by a micro/macro approach [8].

As explained the previous section, using two subvolumes approach leads to a too stiff macroscopic response. In order to correct this problem, and to identify the damageable behaviour, we have chosen to compare macroscopic results and virtual tests. Knowing the behaviour of each constituent (fiber,

matrix and interface) and using an elementary periodic cell, it is possible to model tests that are unrealisable experimentally; these calculations are called virtual tests or numerical experiments. Description of the behaviour of the constituents and of the appropriate elementary cell can be found in [14]. For example it is possible to perform simulations such as :

- all the constituents are considered as elastic and damage behavior is taken into account; in this case it is possible to identify and to validate the damage law introduced in the macroscopic model.
- the matrix viscoplasticity is taken into account, and the interface is perfect. These models allow to correct the macroscopic viscoplastic behaviour of the composite. This correction consists in modifying some terms of the localisation tensor \mathbf{B}_m . This correction is independent of the temperature.

Figure 2 shows a comparison between modellisation and experimental results for transverse tensile tests at different temperatures. Due to the importance of the residual stresses, the whole fabrication process has been taken into account in these modellisations.

2. Polymer matrix composite

As explained in the introduction, the damage behaviour of the matrix is not taken into account. Only, the visco-elastic character of the polymer is taken into account. It is described by a spectral visco-elastic model defined as follows :

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{L} : (\boldsymbol{\epsilon} - \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_a) \quad (10)$$

with,

$$\dot{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}_a = g \sum_i \dot{\boldsymbol{\xi}}_i \quad (11)$$

$$\dot{\boldsymbol{\xi}}_i = \frac{1}{\tau_i} (\mu_i g \mathbf{L}_r^{-1} : \boldsymbol{\sigma} - \boldsymbol{\xi}_i) \quad (12)$$

The spectrum τ_i is defined by the relations :

$$\tau_i = \exp(n_i) \quad (13) \quad \mu_i = \frac{1}{n_o \sqrt{\pi}} \exp\left(-\left(\frac{n - n_c}{n_o}\right)^2\right) \quad (14)$$

$$g(\boldsymbol{\sigma}) = 1 + \beta (\sqrt{\boldsymbol{\sigma} : \mathbf{L}_r^{-1} : \boldsymbol{\sigma}}) \quad (15)$$

In an isotropic case, only 10 parameters have to be identified:

- The 2 elastic constants E_m and ν_m
- The 2 spectral parameters describing the gaussian shape
- The viscous tensor C_R which is considered to be isotropic
- The non-linear function $g(\boldsymbol{\sigma})$

Parameters are directly identified from creep and tensile tests on **neat resin samples**.

It has been shown that the viscous parameters of the polymer matrix behaviour (the spectrum and the function g) depends on the temperature and on the thermodynamic states of the resin. It has also been shown that the T_g of the neat resin samples ($T_{g,0} = 490\text{K}$) was greater than that of the resin inside the composites ($T_{g,c0} = 480\text{K}$). Shieffer [11] has proposed a model to predict the mechanical behaviour of the resin as a function of temperature and of T_g (see the paper [15] presented at this conference).

It is thus possible to predict the behaviour of the ply using a two-subvolume sequential method (micro/meso scale transition). In this case, the correction consists in modifying the viscous tensor using virtual tests. The global composite behaviour is determined using a meso/macro change of scale

(TFA method where the localization and influence tensors are determined analytically [11]). Figure 3 shows a comparison of numerical and experimental results for creep tests on a $[45; -45]_{4s}$ laminate.

Figure 2 : comparison between numerical and experimental results for transverse tensile tests on a SiC/Ti composite at different temperature.

Figure 3 : comparison between numerical and experimental results for creep tests on a $[+/-45^\circ]_{4s}$ IMS/977-2 composite at 120°C and 20/40/60MPa.

APPLICATION TO STRUCTURAL MODELLING

1. Bladed Ring reinforced by SiC/Ti

Numerical procedure

A complete simulation of the bling (Bladed rING) component reinforced with the SM1140+/Ti-6242 composite was carried out. The actual structure is shown in figure 4a. The axisymmetric mesh and the symmetry conditions are shown in figure 4b. The homogeneous part consists of non reinforced titanium. The SiC/Ti composite reinforcement is modeled (i) by meshing all the fibers (denoted "reference modeling") or (figure 4c) or (ii) by the sequential model presented in this paper (figure 4b). The simulation consists of a centrifugal loading. The speed of rotation, chosen arbitrary, varies linearly over time and the duration of the loading is 30s. In order to simplify the comparison, the fiber/matrix interface is supposed to be perfectly bonded. The simulation is divided into three main steps : (i) the manufacturing process (cooling down from 900°C to 25°C), (ii) thermal loading (from 25°C to operating temperature) and (iii) centrifugal loading.

Figure 4 : Modelling of the bladed ring structure (a) real structure, (b) mesh and boundary condition and (c) detail of the mesh when all the fibres are modelled.

Results

From a global point of view (deformation of the structure), the results (not presented here) show a good agreement between the different approaches. An advantage of the multiscale modeling, as compared with the purely macroscopic phenomenological ones, is to provide local information, such as stress and strain fields (finely for the integrated model, average quantities for the sequential approach). Figure 5 presents the mean of the axial stress in the fibre along the last row of fibres (see figure 4). It can be seen that a very good agreement exists between the two approaches. Of course, the “reference modelling” gives a very good description of the stress and strain field at the local scale, but the “two-subvolume sequential model” is sufficient to apply classical lifetime models at the local scale (rupture of fibre, creep/fatigue model in the matrix).

2. Polymer matrix composite structure

Numerical procedure

In this part, a model of a stiffening panel is presented. The mesh and boundary conditions are presented in figure 6. The loading consists of applying a pressure on the surface noted “press” . The pressure is first linearly applied (from time 0. to time 50. seconds) and maintained at a constant value. The material is a IMS/977 $[+/-45^\circ]_{4s}$ composite; two states of ageing are considered : (1) without ageing and (2) curve obtained after 3 months of ageing at 423K. As explain in a previous section, the ageing is introduced in the matrix. The micro/meso change of scale is performed using the TFA method and the meso/macro one using multilayer finite element.

Figure 5 : mean axial stress in the fibre as a function of the position of the fibre obtained by a sequential model and the “reference modelling”.

Figure 7 : global response of a stiffening panel (submitted to a constant loading) as a function of the ageing time.

Figure 6 : Mesh and boundary conditions of the stiffening panel.

Results

The displacement of the face noted "press" as a function of time is presented in figure 7. It can be seen on this figure that the ageing has a great effects on the non-linear response of the structure. After 3 months of ageing at 423K, the structure exhibits a lower non-linear behaviour.

As compared with a classical macroscopic model, the composite behaviour has not been re-identified. Using a multiscale approach, it is possible to predict the ageing effect directly on the structure behaviour.

A comparison has been carried out between a two-subvolume integrated model, and a two-subvolume sequential model. The results are the same, but the computational cost is lower for the sequential approach.

CONCLUSION

The present paper is devoted to the multiscale modelling of non-linear composites. In this paper, the scale changes have been carried out using the TFA method. It permits to describe composite behaviour using micromechanics information.

This approach has been applied to two kinds of composites (Metal Matrix Composites and Polymer Matrix Composites). The comparison between experimental and numerical results are in good agreement. The multiscale approach has been used on structural computation and permits to predict the influence of local effects on the global behaviour of the structure.

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